

The Corrosion Behaviour of Copper in Acid Medium in Presence of Cyanoguanidine

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The effect of cyanoguanidine as inhibitor on the corrosion behaviour of copper metal in 0.1M of both H₂SO₄ and HCl solutions has been studied. The protection efficiency reached about 73% in presence of such inhibitor at 0.5M concentration. The corrosion process is partially anodically controlled. The results are analysed in term of the formation of a protective film on the metal surface. The percentage inhibition and the degree of coverage are found to be higher in HCl than in H₂SO₄ for comparable inhibitor concentrations.

The particular interest in the general field of organic inhibitors is the nature of the chemical bond at the metal surface and an explanation of why these substance often provide such excellent protection when, as in the case of cyanoguanidine on copper, the protective film is of the order of molecular dimension only. Since many inhibitors form stable complexes with metal ions, 'the film theory of protective activity' proposed by Balezin¹ may be used to explain the inhibition efficiency of such compounds. According to this theory, inhibition is due to the formation on the metallic surface of a layer produced by reaction between the metal, the inhibitor and the corrosive ions. The solubility of such corrosion products determines whether an organic compound acts as a corrosion inhibitor or stimulator, corresponding to low and high solubilities respectively. The addition of anodic inhibitors to sulphuric acid solution shifts the potential towards less negative values as a result of a decrease in metal surface. Thus, the adsorbed inhibitors can retard the corrosion². Addition of compounds containing a polar atom such as nitrogen or sulphur facilitates the attachment of the additives to the metal³.

The present study aims to investigate the effect of cyanoguanidine on the corrosion behaviour of copper metal in 0.1M of both H₂SO₄ and HCl solutions.

Results and Discussion

Potential-time measurements: The open-circuit potential of copper electrode immersed in aerated 0.1M of both H₂SO₄ and HCl acids in absence and in presence of cyanoguanidine in the concentration range 5×10^{-2} to $5 \times 10^{-1} M$, was followed as a function of time till the steady state values were established. The steady state potential (E_{corr}) is the potential at which the metal dissolution (anodic) and electronation (cathodic) reaction rates are equal⁴. The addition of such inhibitor alters the anodic rate and consequently corrosion potential

is shifted. The open-circuit potential of copper in 0.1M H₂SO₄ containing different concentrations (5×10^{-5} to $5 \times 10^{-1} M$) of cyanoguanidine was also followed as a function of time till steady state values were obtained. The same also was done for HCl. The result of these measurements are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. It is obvious that the potential shifts with time to

Fig. 1. Relation between potential of copper and time in HCl solutions in presence of cyanoguanidine: (1) blank, (2) 5×10^{-2} , (3) 1×10^{-1} , (4) 2×10^{-1} (5) $5 \times 10^{-1} M$.

Fig. 2. Relation between potential of copper and time in H₂SO₄ solutions in presence of cyanoguanidine: (1) blank, (2) 5×10^{-2} , (3) 1×10^{-1} , (4) 2×10^{-1} and (5) $5 \times 10^{-1} M$.

the active direction till the steady state is attained after about 60 min for H_2SO_4 and HCl. The steady state potential values (E_{corr}) shifted towards a negative direction with the increase of concentration of the inhibitor.

The results indicate that the corrosion behaviour of copper in H_2SO_4 and HCl solutions containing different concentration of cyanoguanidine is generally the same. Thus, it can be concluded that the corrosion process is partially anodically controlled and the inhibitor used is considered as cathodic inhibitor⁵. The corrosion process is controlled by the rate of anodic reaction, while the inhibitor suppresses the cathodic reaction only because of increasing the active parts of the electrode. In all of the tested solutions, E_{corr} are shifted towards negative values and are accompanied by a decrease in the corrosion rate of copper.

Polarisation measurements: The corrosion current i_{corr} was obtained by extrapolating the cathodic Tafel line to the experimentally measured free corrosion potential. From Fig. 3 it is clear that the [inhibitor] has a strong effect on the corrosion behaviour of copper during the cathodic polarisation measurements in 0.1M HCl with increasing the inhibitor concentrations, the free corrosion potential of h.e.r. and Tafel line are shifted to more cathodic potential to the blank curve and Tafel slope slightly increases, indicating that the organic substance used is a cathodic inhibitor.

Fig. 3. Cathodic polarisation of copper electrode in 0.1M HCl solution at different [cyanoguanidine]: (1) blank, (2) 5×10^{-2} , (3) 1×10^{-1} , (4) 2×10^{-1} and 5×10^{-1} M.

Meyer⁶ suggested that the thicker the film, the lower is (α) transfer coefficient for H^+ ion discharge (the higher the cathodic Tafel slope). Higher values of the cathodic Tafel slope in case of the investigated copper suggest that the spontaneously formed passive film is relatively more thick than the corresponding one formed in blank acid⁷.

Decrease in transfer coefficient and corrosion current i_{corr} with increasing inhibitor concentration demonstrates the efficiency of cyanoguanidine as corrosion inhibitor (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF CYANO GUANIDINE ON TRANSFER COEFFICIENT (α) AND CORROSION CURRENT (i_{corr}) IN 0.1M H_2SO_4 AND HCl SOLUTIONS

Inhibitor concn. (M)	H_2SO_4		HCl	
	α	i_{corr} ($\mu A cm^{-2}$)	α	i_{corr} ($\mu A cm^{-2}$)
Blank	0.400	5.00	0.380	2.00
5×10^{-2}	0.380	4.00	0.384	1.30
1×10^{-1}	0.370	2.25	0.374	0.89
2×10^{-1}	0.367	1.00	0.352	0.75
5×10^{-1}	0.362	0.80	0.332	0.64

Rate of corrosion measurements: The corrosion rate of copper metal in 0.1M of both H_2SO_4 and HCl containing the above mentioned inhibitor was calculated from the cathodic polarisation results (Table 2). The corrosion current i_{corr} measurements can be converted to weight-loss data. To

TABLE 2—CORROSION RATE OF Cu METAL IN 0.1M OF BOTH H_2SO_4 AND HCl SOLUTIONS CONTAINING DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF CYANO GUANIDINE

Cyanoguanidine concn. (M)	Corrosion rate ($\times 10^{-3}$ mg cm^{-2} h ⁻¹)	
	H_2SO_4	HCl
0	5.20	2.08
5×10^{-2}	4.16	1.35
1×10^{-1}	2.34	0.92
2×10^{-1}	1.44	0.78
5×10^{-1}	0.83	0.66

determine rate of corrosion based on corrosion current measurements, the following equation can be used,

$$i_{corr} = 0.96W \quad (1)$$

where i_{corr} is the corrosion current ($mA cm^{-2}$) and W is the corrosion rate ($mg cm^{-2} h^{-1}$) which can be calculated over a period of hours⁸.

Fig. 4 show the variation of the protective efficiency ($I\%$) of copper metal as a function of the concentration of cyanoguanidine in 0.1M of both H_2SO_4 and HCl acids solution at 25°. The percentage inhibition increases with the increase in the inhibitor concentration which is greater in HCl than H_2SO_4 acid.

The above results are similar to those reported for the inhibition of copper by triazole⁹ and benzotriazole¹⁰, where the mechanism of inhibition is

Fig. 4. The effect of [inhibitor] on the protection efficiency at 30° for copper in (1) HCl and (2) H₂SO₄.

Fig. 5. Relation between corrosion rate of copper and [inhibitor] in (1) HCl and (2) H₂SO₄.

attributed to the formation of an insoluble copper-triazole film on the metal surface.

Fig. 5 shows the variation of the corrosion rate of copper in 0.1M of both H₂SO₄ and HCl at 25° as a function of the concentration of the inhibitor. It has been indicated⁵ that the film formation approach seems to be conceived. The surface active substance containing atoms with electron pairs becomes protonated, thereafter complex formation with copper cation occurs. Therefore, the formation of complexes (on the surface) may affect the cathodic or anodic areas. Consequently, the steady state potential E_{corr} shifts in either negative or positive direction on which reaction is affected more⁵.

Within a certain range of inhibitor and temperature, where monolayer adsorption is readily maintained over the copper surface, the Langmuir adsorption isotherm may be expressed,

$$\theta/(1-\theta) = AC \exp(-Q/RT) \quad (2)$$

where A is a constant dependent on characteristics of the system of adsorption, C the [inhibitor], Q the heat of adsorption, B the occupied area and $(1-\theta)$ the vacant sites not occupied by the inhibitor. The degree of coverage θ is given by

$$\theta = 1 - W_2/W_1 \quad (3)$$

where W_2 and W_1 are the corrosion rates in solutions with and without inhibitor respectively. Equation (2) can be presented in the form,

$$\log \theta/(1-\theta) = \log A + \log C - Q/2.3 RT \quad (4)$$

Thus a plot of $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ against $\log C$ should be linear at constant temperature. This expectation is realised from the plots in Fig. 6 and within a certain range of approximation the curves are linear but no general agreement with simple Langmuir adsorption curves can be claimed over a wide range of concentration.

Fig. 6. Relation between $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ and \log [inhibitor] for copper in (1) HCl and (2) H₂SO₄.

Experimental

The electrode used were in the form of rods (1 cm × 0.5 cm dia) of spectroscopically pure copper (Johnson and Mathey). The electrode surface was degreased, abraded successively with very fine emery paper and a soft cloth, then thoroughly washed with distilled water and rinsed with the electrolyte to be used.

The potential of the copper electrodes immersed in the test solution was followed as a function of time by means of a manual potentiometer (versus a saturated calomel electrode). Measurements were carried out until a steady state potential value was reached at 25°.

The corrosion rate was determined by the polarisation method. The concentration of the inhibited solution studied in 0.1M H₂SO₄ and HCl varied between 5×10^{-2} and $5 \times 10^{-1}M$.

The electrode vessel used was made of pyrex glass without rubber connection and could accommodate a volume of 60 ml of the test solutions. The cell used for polarisation measurements had two compartments separated by a fritted glass disc to prevent mixing of anolyte and catholyte. The cathodic polarisation curves were obtained using a simple galvanostatic technique in absence (blank)

and in presence of cyanoguanidine. Potentials were measured with reference to a saturated calomel electrode with a fine Luggin capillary positioned close to the electrode surface in order to minimise ohmic potential drop. The copper electrodes were cathodically polarised using a constant device (type Leybold, Germany). In the galvanostatic method the current was passed and after 3 min the potential was measured. Then the current was changed to a new level and so on.

The inhibition efficiency ($I\%$) of the inhibitor was calculated using equation,

$$I\% = 100 (1 - W_2/W_1) \quad (5)$$

where W_2 and W_1 are the corrosion rates in solutions with and without the inhibitor respectively¹¹.

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